

Estimating Grazingland Acres for Desired Geographies Using Machine Learning Methods

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to develop a robust methodology for accurately estimating the acreage of rangeland and pastureland within specified geographic regions, with a particular focus on Ecoregion Level 3. This study utilizes image photo interpretation data from the National Resource Inventory (NRI), a well-established longitudinal survey designed to assess conditions and trends of soil, water, and related resources on non-federal lands of the United States. However, the weights of NRI data are developed to represent non-federal land of states only, and the number of points within the target region may be limited. In this paper, we employ a model-assisted approach that integrates satellite-based Cropland Data Layer (CDL) data as auxiliary information through machine learning techniques to enhance the accuracy of acreage estimates. The proposed methodology involves three key steps: first, estimating the relationship between rangeland and pastureland indicators within the survey data and numerous CDL variables; second, applying this relationship to generate rangeland and pastureland probabilities across the entire U.S. map; and third, extracting the specific regions of interest from this imputed map to calculate the acreage of rangeland and pastureland. In this study, we observe that the use of the Random Forest model increases the highest mean AUC to 0.950, which suggests that the new model-based estimator serves as a reliable alternative to the conventional design-based estimator from the NRI.

Key Words: Survey, Model-based Approach, Cropland Data Layer (CDL), Machine Learning

1 Introduction

The conservation of natural resources is critical for sustaining agricultural productivity. The National Resource Conservation Services, a division of the United States Department of Agriculture, has played a pivotal role in the development, implementation, and evaluation of various conservation activities. The Conservation Effects Assessment Project (CEAP), initiated in 2003, seeks to provide scientific insights into the impacts and advantages of USDA's conservation efforts (J and A. (2019)). CEAP's Grazing Land component primarily evaluates conservation practices on rangeland, pastureland, and grazed forests, among other non-cropped agricultural producing areas. C et al. (2017) prioritizes parameters such as non-federal rangeland and pastureland acreage across US states, estimated using design-based small-area estimation methods. These methods rely on data from the

National Resources Inventory (NRI), a longitudinal survey that supports the establishment of agricultural and environmental policies and the implementation of related programs.

Rangeland and pastureland are two distinct land cover categories, each characterized by the type of vegetation and management practices involved. According to the NRI data collection instructions, rangeland is defined as a type of grassland where the predominant vegetation consists of grasses, grass-like plants, or forbs. This land is typically managed through the manipulation of grazing, with the vegetation either naturally occurring or artificially revegetated. In contrast, pastureland is managed primarily for the production of introduced forage plants, often for livestock grazing. Pastureland cover may include single species or mixtures of grasses and legumes, and its management generally involves intensive cultural treatments such as fertilization, weed control, reseeding, and grazing management. Unlike rangeland, pastureland is more actively managed for agricultural purposes, including livestock grazing and erosion control.

In this study, we transition the geographical units from U.S. states to alternative regional delineation: Ecoregion Level 3. Ecoregions represent areas where ecosystems, including the type, quality, and quantity of environmental resources, share general similarities. These regions serve as a crucial spatial framework for the research, assessment, and monitoring of ecosystems and their components. Ecoregions are essential for structuring and implementing ecosystem management strategies across various nongovernmental organizations that manage diverse resources within the same geographic areas (Omernik and Griffith (2014) and McMahon et al. (2001)). By transitioning to Ecoregion Level 3, the study adopts a more ecologically relevant approach, better aligning with the natural distribution of resources and enhancing the effectiveness of management and conservation strategies.

The goal of this project is to accurately estimate acres of grazingland (pastureland or rangeland) for a new domain which might be different from the domains considered in the sampling stage. Because we did not control the sample size designated to this new domain, we might end up with a small sample size in the new domain. Satellite-based data, such as the Cropland Data Layer, a georeferenced, crop-specific land cover dataset, is proposed as suitable auxiliary data. The use of auxiliary information in survey data estimation has a strong foundation in model-based small-area estimation methods, as established in seminal works by Fay and Herriot (1979); Battese et al. (1988). These model-based small area estimators are known for achieving greater efficiency than design-based estimators by effectively utilizing auxiliary data, which is often assumed to be available for the entire population.

Satellite-based data sources have been extensively utilized as auxiliary data in estimating land use areas. Battese et al. (1988) utilized data from the Land Observatory Satellites to predict average crop areas by applying a linear mixed model at the unit level. For similar analytical challenges, Datta and Ghosh (1991) introduced a hierarchical Bayes approach, while You and Rao (2002) proposed a pseudo-empirical best linear unbiased prediction estimator. Wang et al. (2018) estimated land cover proportions using Cropland Data Layer data. Furthermore, Kim et al. (2018) and Erciulescu et al. (2020) examined crop area estimation at the state level and county level, incorporating multiple auxiliary data sources, including CDL.

This research focuses on very small classified units. The target region is divided into a fine grid of square tiles. For each tile, the proportion of pixels corresponding to each CDL category serves as an auxiliary variable, while the rangeland/pastureland indicator acts as the binary response variable. The topic of small-area estimation for binary outcomes has been explored by numerous researchers. For instance, Ghosh et al. (1998) developed Bayesian predictors using a hierarchical generalized linear model with normally distributed random effects. This approach was extended by Moura and Migon (2002) to incorporate spatially structured priors. Jiang (2003) introduced the empirical best prediction method employing a generalized linear mixed model, offering an alternative to the hierarchical Bayesian method. Additionally, Malec and Müller (2008) proposed a Bayesian semi-parametric hierarchical GLM incorporating both parametric and nonparametric random effects. Molina et al. (2007) and López-Vizcaíno et al. (2013) advanced SAE using a multinomial

logit mixed model approach. More recently, Sun et al. (2021) introduced SAE through a conditionally specified bivariate mixed-effects model for binary and Gaussian variables.

In contrast to most studies that rely on a limited number of auxiliary variables, this research incorporates a comprehensive set of candidates from 138 CDL categories. Similarly, Jang et al. (2024) also adopts a comprehensive set of candidate variables. However, while Jang et al. (2024) employs the LASSO method (Tibshirani (1996)), which applies an L1 penalty to shrink some estimator values to zero, LASSO presents notable limitations. Specifically, it tends to select only one variable from a group of highly correlated variables, which can lead to instability in model selection. Moreover, it struggles with selecting the correct model when the true underlying relationship is more complex than linear. In addition, Jang et al. (2024) limits their analysis to estimating the rangeland acreage at the state level and county level. Given these limitations, it is reasonable to explore alternative machine learning methods that might offer superior performance. Furthermore, applying these methods to other regions of interest, such as Ecoregion Level 3, and extending their use to estimate the acreage of other land types, such as pastureland, is both meaningful and valuable for enhancing the breadth of land cover analysis.

This investigation presents a small area estimation approach utilizing various machine learning techniques. Specifically, we employ Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and LightGBM to enhance the accuracy of our estimates. The use of machine learning methods is particularly advantageous when dealing with a large number of variables or features, as these methods excel in managing high-dimensional data and identifying complex patterns. By employing these techniques, we can effectively reduce model bias and improve predictive performance. Model performance is evaluated by measuring the discrepancy between model-based estimates and design-based estimates from the National Resources Inventory (NRI), with different models compared based on their prediction accuracies. This approach demonstrates the meaningful application of machine learning in situations where traditional methods may struggle due to the large volume of variables, offering a more precise estimation framework.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a comprehensive overview of the National Resources Inventory (NRI) survey and the Cropland Data Layer (CDL) dataset, illustrating how these two datasets are integrated for analysis. Section 3 describes the model setup and introduces the model-based imputation estimator employed in this study. Section 4 presents the results of the model comparison and rangeland estimation at the Ecoregion Level 3, while Section 5 focuses on the model comparison and pastureland estimation at the Ecoregion Level 3. Section 6 offers a discussion of the findings and their broader implications. In the Appendix, an adjustment method is introduced to align our state-level estimates with the NRI's published data, ensuring consistency between our findings and established benchmarks.

2 Data

NRI is a longitudinal survey administered by the NRCS in collaboration with Iowa State University. The NRI is a panel study of land use and associated natural resource characteristics, conducted every five years from 1982 to 1997 and annually since 2000. For studies at 5-year intervals from 1982 to 1997, all 300,000 segments of the foundation sample were observed; however, for yearly studies after 2000, only 70,000 segments, a subset of the whole sample, have been observed. NRI collects data primarily through the visual interpretation of aerial photography, complemented by local data collection and the incorporation of administrative information. The rangeland/pastureland indicator can be derived from the NRI data using the land use information of each sample point.

CDL is a georeferenced raster map established by the USDA's National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS). This dataset offers crop and other particular land cover classifications with resolutions of either 30 meters or 56 meters, derived from remote sensing technology, and it covers the contigu-

ous United States on an annual basis Han et al. (2012). In this study, we utilized the 2017 Cropland Data Layer (CDL) data with a resolution of 30 in conjunction with the 2017 National Resources Inventory (NRI) survey. For rangeland analysis, we focused on seventeen U.S. states that include non-federal rangeland areas, while for pastureland, our analysis encompassed all 48 contiguous states.

To construct a statistical model, we collect data from square tiles of CDL pixels (each pixel has a resolution of 30 by 30 meters) centered on the closest pixel to an NRI sample point, as seen in Figure 1, and then identify the CDL category of each pixel inside each tile. Each number in the figure presents the ID number of each pixel. A pixel that is closer to the NRI sampling point is typically assigned a lower ID number.

Investigating the impact of different square tile sizes on model performance is essential for optimizing predictive accuracy. Smaller square tiles tend to capture more relevant information at NRI sample locations, but if the tiles are too small, they may lead to insufficient data, thereby increasing estimator variability. On the other hand, larger square tiles may incorporate extraneous features, potentially introducing bias into the estimators. To explore this trade-off, we conducted a comparative analysis using South Dakota data, as detailed in Section 4, evaluating square tile sizes of 1×1 , 3×3 , 5×5 , and 7×7 .

Figure 1: The sequence numbers of observations are derived from a 7×7 grid of pixels centered on the pixel closest to an NRI sample point. The boundaries of the different tile sizes are as follows: the black boundary represents a 1×1 square tile, the red boundary indicates a 3×3 square tile, the blue boundary signifies a 5×5 square tile, and the green boundary corresponds to a 7×7 square tile.

To extract usable information from the CDL data, we compute the proportion of pixels belonging to each specific category and utilize this information to estimate the acres of rangeland/pastureland in regions of interest. Given that the CDL encompasses 169 distinct categories, employing machine learning methods, as detailed in Section 3, provides significant advantages. Traditional statistical methods may struggle with a large number of predictors, leading to issues such as overfitting and inefficiency. Machine learning techniques, on the other hand, are specifically designed to handle large numbers of variables, enabling more robust feature selection and improved predictive accuracy. This approach enhances our ability to accurately estimate rangeland and pastureland in the targeted regions

3 Statistical Methodologies

In this section, we provide the small area estimation (SAE) approach employed for predicting rangeland and pastureland indicators using various machine learning models. First, we define the response variable and corresponding covariates utilized in the analysis. Next, we detail the machine learning methods applied in this study, highlighting their role in model development. Then, we describe the model-based estimator used to calculate the rangeland and pastureland areas, providing a comprehensive framework for the estimation process. Finally, we provide a description of the Jackknife method employed to estimate the variance of our model-based estimator.

To demonstrate the statistical model utilized, we define the following notation: For the i th NRI sample point in the target region, where $i = 1, \dots, n$,

$$Y_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the } i\text{th NRI sample point represents rangeland or pastureland,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$X_{ij} = \frac{\text{(the number of pixels belonging to category } j \text{ within the square tile.)}}{\text{(the total number of pixels within the square tile.)}},$$

for $j = 1, \dots, p$,

where p represents the selected number of CDL categories used in this region. X_{ij} denotes the percentage of category j within the square tile surrounding the i th NRI point. Let $\mathbf{X}_i = (X_{i1}, \dots, X_{ip})^T$ for all i . Table 1 provides an example of the data obtained using this method.

Table 1: An example of data

ID	X_1	X_2	...	X_p	Y
1	0.06	0	...	0.91	1
2	0	0.22	...	0	0
3	0.8	0.12	...	0	1

Building on the analysis of square tile sizes, it is equally important to compare the performance of different modeling approaches. To this end, we employed a 10-fold cross-validation methodology, as detailed in Section 4, to evaluate and compare four models. The first is logistic regression with LASSO, which uses penalization for feature selection. The other is LightGBM, an efficient gradient-boosting machine. We also considered Support Vector Machines (SVM), known for maximizing the margin between classes using kernel functions for non-linear data. Lastly, Random Forest, an ensemble method, builds multiple decision trees to improve prediction accuracy and reduce overfitting. This comprehensive comparison is essential for identifying the model that offers the best balance of prediction accuracy, bias, and variance, ensuring that the most reliable method is selected for predicting rangeland and pastureland acreage. Notably, all machine learning algorithms involve hyperparameters, and varying their values can significantly influence model predictions. In this study, cross-validation is employed to identify the optimal set of hyperparameters for these four models.

3.1 Logistic Regression and LASSO GLM

Given that the response variable is a binary indicator for rangeland and pastureland, the probability $P(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i)$ can be modeled using a logistic regression model, which is widely recognized as a standard approach for binary outcomes. In this context, we specify the logistic regression model to

include the main effect terms of the covariates, X_i , as follows:

$$P(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i; \boldsymbol{\beta}) = \pi(\mathbf{X}_i; \boldsymbol{\beta}) = \frac{\exp\left(\beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j X_{ij}\right)}{1 + \exp\left(\beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j X_{ij}\right)}, \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_p)^T$.

Then, $l(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, the log-likelihood function of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$, is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} l(\boldsymbol{\beta}) &= \sum_{i=1}^n \{Y_i \log(P(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i; \boldsymbol{\beta})) + (1 - Y_i) \log(P(Y_i = 0 | \mathbf{X}_i; \boldsymbol{\beta}))\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \left\{ Y_i \mathbf{X}_i^T \boldsymbol{\beta} - \log(1 + \exp(\mathbf{X}_i^T \boldsymbol{\beta})) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

When the number of predictors is large, LASSO becomes a valuable tool. LASSO is a penalized regression model that simultaneously addresses the challenges of variable selection and regularization. In high-dimensional datasets, where many predictors may be irrelevant or redundant, LASSO helps to streamline the model by shrinking the coefficients of less important variables to zero. This approach not only simplifies the model but also reduces the risk of overfitting. The LASSO estimator of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is calculated by minimizing the following objective function:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^{\text{Lasso}} = \underset{\boldsymbol{\beta}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left\{ -l(\boldsymbol{\beta}) + \lambda \|\boldsymbol{\beta}\|_{l_1} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where $l(\boldsymbol{\beta})$ represents the log-likelihood function of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ in (2), $\|\cdot\|_{l_1}$ denotes the l_1 norm, and $\lambda > 0$ is the regularization parameter. The role of λ is to control the degree of shrinkage applied to the estimator of $\boldsymbol{\beta}$. This shrinkage reduces the variance of the estimator by introducing some bias, thereby improving model stability. The optimal value of λ is determined through cross-validation, where the goal is to minimize prediction error by selecting the λ that offers the best balance between bias and variance.

3.2 LightGBM

While LASSO addresses the challenge of managing a large number of predictors, it remains limited as a linear model. To capture potential nonlinear patterns, we incorporate LightGBM, a gradient boosting framework that uses tree-based learning algorithms, specifically designed for efficiency and scalability with large datasets. For binary classification tasks, LightGBM models the probability using the logistic function:

$$\hat{P}^{\text{LGBM}}(Y_i = 1 | X_i) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-f(X_i)}} \quad (4)$$

Where $f(X_i)$ is the output of the decision trees built by LightGBM, which is a real-valued score. In datasets with numerous features, LightGBM helps to identify patterns and relationships by constructing decision trees that focus on reducing error at each iteration. Using decision trees as weak

learners, LightGBM optimizes a regularized objective function, which can be expressed as follows:

$$\hat{f}(X_i) = \operatorname{argmin}_{f(X_i)} \sum_{i=1}^n l(Y_i, \hat{P}^{\text{LGBM}}(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i)) + \Omega(f(X_i)) \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{f}(X_i)$ is the learned function and $l(Y_i, \hat{P}^{\text{LGBM}}(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i))$ is the loss function, we employ the log loss (binary cross entropy) function for classification. $\Omega(f(X_i))$ is the regularization term to avoid overfitting, typically involving the complexity of the model. During the process of optimizing the objective function, LightGBM builds trees sequentially, where each new tree corrects the errors of the previous ones. The optimization for each iteration t can be expressed as:

$$f^{(t)}(\mathbf{X}_i) = f^{(t-1)}(\mathbf{X}_i) + \eta h^{(t)}(\mathbf{X}_i) \quad (6)$$

where $f^{(t)}(\mathbf{X}_i)$ is the current model, $h^{(t)}(\mathbf{X}_i)$ represents the weak learner (decision tree), and η denotes the learning rate. Unlike level-wise tree growth (where all leaves are split simultaneously), LightGBM grows trees leaf-wise. The split is performed on the leaf with the largest potential loss reduction, leading to a more optimized structure. This often results in faster training times and better accuracy.

3.3 SVM

Support Vector Machines (SVM) is a powerful supervised learning algorithm particularly well-suited for classification tasks. Developed by Cortes and Vapnik (1995), SVM aims to find the optimal hyperplane that best separates data points from different classes while maximizing the margin between them. The objective function for SVM is defined as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{w}, b} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{w}\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i \quad (7)$$

subject to:

$$Y_i (\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{X}_i + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad \xi_i \geq 0$$

where \mathbf{w} is the normal vector to the hyperplane, b is the intercept, C is a regularization parameter controlling the trade-off between maximizing the margin and minimizing classification errors. Next, SVM computes a decision function $f(\mathbf{X}_i) = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{X}_i + b$, which represents the signed distance of a data point from the hyperplane. Platt Scaling then applies the logistic transformation:

$$\hat{P}^{\text{SVM}}(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(Af(\mathbf{X}_i) + B)}$$

where A and B are parameters learned from the training data using cross-validation. Additionally, SVM can handle non-linear classification through the use of kernel functions, which transform the input space into higher dimensions. In this study, we employed various kernels, including the Radial Basis Function (RBF), polynomial, and sigmoid kernels, and determined the best-performing kernel through cross-validation.

3.4 Random Forest

Random Forest is the other highly effective algorithm for handling datasets with a large number of features. Developed by Breiman (2001), it is an ensemble learning method that builds multiple decision trees during training and outputs the mode of the classes for classification from the individual trees. By selecting a random subset of features for each tree, Random Forest ensures that the model remains both efficient and scalable. The objective function for Random Forest can be expressed as the aggregation of the predictions from all decision trees in the forest:

$$\hat{P}^{\text{RF}}(Y_i = 1|\mathbf{X}_i) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \hat{P}_t(Y_i = 1|\mathbf{X}_i) \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{P}^{\text{RF}}(Y_i = 1|\mathbf{X}_i)$ represents the final prediction, T is the total number of trees, and $\hat{P}_t(Y_i = 1|\mathbf{X}_i)$ is the probability estimate from the t -th tree for input \mathbf{X}_i . The core idea behind Random Forest is to reduce overfitting and improve generalization by averaging the predictions of these decision trees, each trained on different random subsets of the data and features. This bagging technique helps to reduce the variance commonly associated with individual decision trees, making Random Forest a robust and reliable choice for complex datasets.

3.5 Model-based Estimator

Now, we illustrate the model-based estimator for determining the acreage of rangeland and pastureland within the region of interest and the statistical model employed. First, we construct a grid that fully covers the specific region, where each grid cell is a square consisting of 7×7 pixels. The total number of grid cells that intersect with the region is N . For each grid cell, let W_i represent the number of pixels within the i th cell that overlap with the region. Thus, $0 < W_i \leq 49$ for all i , where $W_i = 49$ indicates that the grid cell fully overlaps with the region, and $W_i < 49$ indicates partial overlap. Figure 2 provides a detailed visual representation of the grid and the corresponding overlap with the region of interest.

Figure 2: An illustration of a grid overlaid on a target area. The ellipse delineates the target area. Red dots indicate NRI sample points classified as rangeland, while blue dots denote NRI sample points classified as non-rangeland.

Since each pixel in the CDL corresponds to 0.2223946 acres, we use $m = 0.2223946$ as the conversion factor to translate the number of pixels into acres. Define η_i as the federal ownership indicator, where $\eta_i = 1$ if the i th square tile is federally owned, and $\eta_i = 0$ otherwise. The true acreage of non-federal rangeland and pastureland within the specific region is given by $T = \sum_{i=1}^N mW_i(1 - \eta_i)Y_i$. The model-based estimator of T , denoted by \hat{T}_m , is then defined as follows:

$$\hat{T}_m = \sum_{i=1}^N mW_i(1 - \eta_i) \left\{ \delta_i Y_i + (1 - \delta_i) \hat{E}[Y_i | \mathbf{X}_i] \right\} \quad (9)$$

In binary response models, the expected value $\hat{E}(Y_i | \mathbf{X}_i)$ represents the probability that the indicator equals 1, given the set of predictors \mathbf{X}_i . Since Y_i can only be 0 or 1, the expected value effectively becomes a probability:

$$\hat{E}(Y_i | \mathbf{X}_i) = 0 \cdot \hat{P}(Y_i = 0 | \mathbf{X}_i) + 1 \cdot \hat{P}(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i) = \hat{P}(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i)$$

Thus, the model-based estimator \hat{T}_m can be computed as follows:

$$\hat{T}_m = \sum_{i=1}^N mW_i(1 - \eta_i) \left\{ \delta_i Y_i + (1 - \delta_i) \hat{P}(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i) \right\} \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{P}(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i)$ is calculated following the methodology described in Sections 3.1 to 3.4 and

$$\delta_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the square tile } i \text{ contains NRI point,} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Notably, in situations where the NRI indicator Y_i is unavailable, a more general model-based estimator could be employed:

$$\hat{T}_m = \sum_{i=1}^N mW_i(1 - \eta_i) \left\{ \hat{E}[Y_i | \mathbf{X}_i] \right\} = \sum_{i=1}^N mW_i(1 - \eta_i) \left\{ \hat{P}(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i) \right\} \quad (11)$$

3.6 Jackknife method

In the study by Jang et al. (2024), the variance of (9) was further evaluated using a parametric bootstrap approach, which relies on the assumption that a sufficient number of NRI points are classified as rangeland. However, this assumption is not satisfied at the Ecoregion level 3, where the number of such NRI points is often insufficient. Consequently, in this study, we employ the Jackknife method to estimate the variance of (9). The Jackknife method is well-suited for this context, as it does not require the same stringent conditions as the parametric bootstrap, allowing for more reliable variance estimation in scenarios where data limitations are present.

We begin by accessing the data file containing all NRI segments within a single Ecoregion level 3 area. The NRI segments within the areas retain the FIPS code of their respective states. These segments are initially sorted by their FIPS codes, ensuring state-level organization, and are subsequently arranged based on their Geo-number, a unique geographic identifier assigned to each NRI survey segment, to provide further spatial structure within each state.

Next, we partition these sorted segments into 29 distinct groups. It is important to note that the

threshold for applying the Central Limit Theorem, the Law of Large Numbers, and similar statistical principles typically involves 30 groups. However, in the early history of the NRI, programmers adopted the use of 29 groups. To maintain consistency with this historical practice, we have continued using 29, which has since become a recognized convention within the NRI:

- **First group:** 1st segment; $(1 + 29)$ th segment; $(1 + 29 \times 2)$ th segment; ...
- **Second group:** 2nd segment; $(2 + 29)$ th segment; $(2 + 29 \times 2)$ th segment; ...
- ...
- **29th group:** 29th segment; $(29 + 29)$ th segment; $(29 + 29 \times 2)$ th segment; ...

This systematic grouping ensures an even distribution of segments across all groups. We then utilize this NRI sample points dataset to generate $\hat{P}^{[k]} (Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_{i,-k})$, where the calculation excludes data from the k th group. Subsequently, we use the probability to compute \hat{T}_{-k} for $k = 1, \dots, 29$ as follows:

$$\hat{T}_{-k} = \sum_{i=1}^N mW_i(1 - \eta_i) \left\{ \delta_i Y_i + (1 - \delta_i) \hat{P}^{[k]} (Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_{i,-k}) \right\}, \quad (12)$$

where $i = 1, \dots, N$ represents the total number of grid cells that intersect with the region of interest. The Jackknife variance estimator for the model-based estimator is subsequently calculated as follows:

$$\text{var}(\hat{T}) = \frac{28}{29} \sum_{k=1}^{29} (\hat{T}_{-k} - \bar{T})^2, \quad (13)$$

where $\bar{T} = \sum_{k=1}^{29} \hat{T}_{-k} / 29$.

4 Results for Rangeland Estimation

In this section, we validate the selection of the Random Forest method by comparing its performance with that of LGBM, SVM, and Lasso, utilizing the rangeland dataset from South Dakota. The South Dakota dataset is chosen due to the availability of a sufficient number of sample points. Additionally, we consider the NRI state-level estimates to be the benchmark, as the NRI exclusively publishes aggregated data at the state level. In contrast, county-level estimates are inherently limited by smaller sample sizes. Moreover, variability across counties presents a significant challenge. As a result, the NRI places greater confidence in state-level estimates rather than county-level estimates.

We also evaluate the impact of different square tile sizes on prediction accuracy, determining that a 7×7 pixel grid offers the most precise results. A comprehensive comparison of the prediction accuracy for LASSO, LGBM, SVM, and Random Forest is then conducted utilizing datasets from 17 U.S. states (Washington, North Dakota, Wyoming, South Dakota, Utah, Oklahoma, Kansas, Colorado, Nebraska, Oregon, California, Arizona, Montana, New Mexico, Nevada, Idaho, Texas) and 58 Ecoregion level 3 areas. We specifically focus on these 17 states, as they are classified as rangeland states. However, some ambiguity exists in the classification, as certain regions fall into grey areas. Although rangeland generally refers to grassland and scrub shrubland located in western states, it has also been identified in Alabama, Arkansas, Louisiana, Missouri, Florida, and Puerto Rico. These details are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Rangeland Map

Nonetheless, for this study, we focus exclusively on the 17 rangeland states. Our findings indicate that the combination of the Random Forest model with the 7×7 square tile size achieves the highest accuracy for rangeland estimates. Furthermore, we found the Jackknife method to be particularly effective for variance estimation at Ecoregion Level 3.

Notably, we present a detailed adjustment methodology designed to align our estimates with the published data of the National Research Institute (NRI). This approach ensures that our findings are consistent with established benchmarks. The technical details of this methodology are provided in the Appendix.

4.1 Comparison of Various Models and Datasets Across Multiple Square Tile Sizes

To assess the impact of varying square tile sizes on model performance, we compare four sizes: 1×1 , 3×3 , 5×5 , and 7×7 , selecting the size that produced the highest prediction accuracy. Furthermore, a 10-fold cross-validation methodology was employed to evaluate and compare the performance of four models: LASSO with optimal λ (LASSO min), LightGBM, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Random Forest.

Table 2 summarizes the mean AUC values across 16 different scenarios, comparing the performance of various models across different square tile sizes and methods. The AUC (Area Under the Curve) serves as a key metric for evaluating prediction accuracy, with higher AUC values indicating better model performance. The results reveal a consistent trend: larger square tiles tend to produce higher

AUC values, suggesting they capture more relevant information for accurate predictions. Consequently, for the imputation estimation of rangeland acreage, we selected the data generated from the largest square tiles. Among the models evaluated, the Random Forest model achieved an AUC exceeding 0.95, indicating outstanding classification accuracy. The combination of the Random Forest model with the 7×7 square tile size offers a robust framework for accurately estimating rangeland acreage.

Table 2: Mean AUCs of South Dakota

Size	LightGBM	SVM	Random Forest	LASSO min
1×1	0.9134	0.8970	0.9133	0.9143
3×3	0.9420	0.9428	0.9441	0.9446
5×5	0.9468	0.9468	0.9488	0.9485
7×7	0.9467	0.9485	0.9510	0.9507

4.2 County-level estimates

To evaluate the accuracy of our model-based estimates of rangeland acreage derived from CDL data, we conducted a comparative analysis against design-based estimates at the county level across South Dakota. Figure 4 is organized in ascending order based on the design-based estimates (NRI). The results reveal a high degree of alignment between the model-based and design-based estimates, particularly for the Random Forest, Lasso, and SVM models. However, the LGBM model exhibits a tendency to overestimate rangeland acreage, indicating a slight deviation from the design-based estimates. The strong overall alignment, with the exception of LGBM, underscores the reliability and validity of these model-based approaches in accurately estimating rangeland acreage at the county level.

Figure 4: Estimates of the rangeland area in each county in South Dakota.

4.3 State-level estimates

Following the county-level comparison, we extended our analysis to the state level, evaluating the model performance across seventeen U.S. states. Table 3 presents the NRI sample sizes, along with the breakdown of rangeland and non-rangeland data points, for each of the seventeen states.

Table 3: NRI observed, rangeland, and non-rangeland data points across seventeen states

State	Sample	Range	Non_Range
Arizona	1616	1127	489
California	5971	1999	3972
Colorado	4826	2040	2786
Idaho	4500	1584	2916
Kansas	5816	1495	4321
Montana	4314	1712	2602
Nebraska	5097	1363	3734
Nevada	1638	1199	439
New Mexico	3434	2209	1225
North Dakota	5898	1215	4683
Oklahoma	4447	1238	3209
Oregon	3709	923	2786
South Dakota	5249	1802	3447
Texas	13670	5623	8047
Utah	1826	821	1005
Washington	3789	559	3230
Wyoming	2629	1673	956

Figure 5 presents the box plots of the mean AUC values for the four different models: Lasso, Light-GBM (lgbm), Random Forest, and SVM across seventeen U.S. states. Notably, all models exhibit relatively high AUC values, with Random Forest and Lasso showing slightly higher median AUCs, indicating strong classification performance across the states analyzed. The consistency and range of AUCs suggest that while all models perform well, there are slight variations in their predictive accuracy, with Random Forest emerging as a particularly robust option for this analysis.

Figure 5: Mean AUC of 17 States

Figure 6 presents a comparison of design-based and model-based estimates of rangeland acreage across seventeen U.S. states, ordered in ascending order based on the design-based estimates. Consistent with the county-level results, the Random Forest, Lasso, and SVM models show a strong alignment with the design-based estimates, underscoring the accuracy and effectiveness of these model-based approaches. In contrast, the LGBM model demonstrates a tendency to overestimate rangeland acreage. This close correspondence for the other models suggests that Random Forest, Lasso, and SVM are particularly reliable for state-level rangeland acreage estimation.

Figure 6: Estimates of the rangeland area in each state

4.4 Ecoregion Level 3 Model estimates

Building upon the county and state-level analyses, we now focus on building models on Ecoregion Level 3 and use estimated relationships to impute the entire map, which represents the primary objective of this project. For this analysis, we employ the LASSO, Random Forest, SVM, and LGBM models, aggregating CDL data using 7×7 grid sections. Table 4 provides the NRI sample sizes, with a detailed breakdown of rangeland and non-rangeland data points, for each of the Ecoregion Level 3 areas.

Based on Table 4, it is evident that several Ecoregion Level 3 areas have an insufficient number of NRI points classified as rangeland, which poses challenges for reliably fitting the models. In these cases, we have combined the affected ecoregions with adjacent ecoregions that produce state-level estimators most closely aligned with the NRI estimators, as detailed in Table 5.

Then, we aim to assess the accuracy of the Ecoregion level 3 models; nevertheless, the absence of design-based estimates at the Ecoregion level 3 presents a challenge, as it limits the availability of a direct benchmark for comparison. For the model-based estimates, we employed an Ecoregion level 3 modeling approach, wherein distinct models were fitted for each ecoregion, allowing for region-specific coefficients. To overcome the lack of Ecoregion level 3 benchmarks, we applied the Ecoregion level 3 model to generate county-level estimates and subsequently compared these with the design-based estimates. This strategy enables an indirect evaluation of the Ecoregion level 3 model's performance by utilizing county-level benchmarks as a proxy for validation.

Table 4: NRI observed, rangeland, and non-rangeland data points across Ecoregion Level 3 areas

Eco	Sample	Range	Non_Range	Eco	Sample	Range	Non_Range
1	1163	52	1111	28	568	330	238
2	699	0	699	29	2157	792	1365
3	713	2	711	30	755	515	240
4	576	21	555	31	1579	1383	196
5	452	84	368	32	1035	218	817
6	1690	695	995	33	1394	353	1041
7	1373	128	1245	34	2338	985	1353
8	121	99	22	35	1787	27	1760
9	683	188	495	36	139	6	133
10	2121	618	1503	37	274	35	239
11	817	351	466	38	29	0	29
12	1935	526	1409	39	112	2	110
13	2233	1256	977	40	1471	207	1264
14	701	508	193	41	51	6	45
15	934	69	865	42	4114	1214	2900
16	279	101	178	43	4912	2658	2254
17	1583	681	902	44	444	331	113
18	1463	951	512	46	4794	595	4199
19	523	242	281	47	2154	66	2088
20	1296	725	571	48	632	37	595
21	1853	765	1088	77	156	13	143
22	1302	866	436	78	692	47	645
23	415	245	170	79	424	342	82
24	1294	917	377	80	1719	1125	594
25	6973	2274	4699	81	1115	644	471
26	3085	2107	978	85	478	166	312
27	6542	1996	4546				

Table 5: Combined Ecoregions

Trouble Eco lv3	n_range	n_nonrange	Combined Eco lv3	n_range	n_nonrange
2	0	699	1	52	1161
3	2	711	4	21	555
38	0	29	37	35	239
39	2	110	40	207	1264

Table 6 provides the number of square tiles (each consisting of 7×7 pixels) for each of the Ecoregion Level 3 areas. Figure 7 displays four comparisons of design-based and model-based estimates of rangeland acreage at the county level across seventeen U.S. states. The model-based estimates were generated using CDL data aggregated into 7×7 grid sections and employed the Ecoregion Level 3 modeling approach. The figure also includes confidence intervals for the design-based estimates, with variances calculated via the Jackknife method. Notably, the Random Forest model exhibits the highest accuracy in estimating rangeland acreage.

Table 6: Number of square tiles across Ecoregion Level 3 areas

Eco	Square Tiles	Eco	Square Tiles	Eco	Square Tiles
1	1270359	19	1047273	37	652048
2	449082	20	3113135	38	324921
3	341545	21	3324792	39	2435539
4	1345120	22	3267640	40	2280718
5	1215110	23	2517179	41	432231
6	1777921	24	3739650	42	3989711
7	1062630	25	6566058	43	8161186
8	360417	26	4533796	44	1347759
9	1212874	27	6286607	46	2867385
10	1900385	28	638526	47	1428376
11	1619428	29	2018995	48	418897
12	1228089	30	1713367	77	693948
13	7029641	31	1219697	78	1104436
14	2904312	32	993148	79	903028
15	1873036	33	1280842	80	3191556
16	1377020	34	1877708	81	2695462
17	3757724	35	3493447	85	480857
18	3018318	36	615057		

(a) Lasso min

(b) Random Forest

(c) LGBM

(d) SVM

Figure 7: County Level Estimates Across 17 States

The imputed map presented in Figure 8 delineates Ecoregion level 3 boundaries and illustrates the predicted probability of rangeland across the 17 states under study. In this visualization, dark green areas correspond to regions with a high probability of being classified as rangeland, whereas light green areas indicate a lower probability. This map is particularly useful as it provides a probabilistic overview of rangeland distribution, allowing for the extraction of specific regions of interest from which the rangeland acreage can be accurately calculated.

Figure 8: Ecoregion boundaries and the predicted probability of rangeland

4.5 Ecoregion Level 3 estimates with Confidence Interval

In this study, we utilize the Jackknife method to estimate the variance of (9). We begin by accessing the data file containing all NRI segments within a single Ecoregion level 3 area. However, certain Ecoregion Level 3 areas lack a sufficient number of NRI rangeland points necessary for effective model fitting. As detailed in Table 7, these Ecoregion Level 3 areas are combined with the nearest Ecoregion Level 3 area to ensure adequate data for analysis. The method used to select these Ecoregion Level 3 combinations follows the same approach introduced in Section 4.4.

Table 7: Ecoregion Level 3 Combinations for Variance Estimation

Trouble Eco lv3	n_range	n_nonrange	Combined Eco lv3	n_range	n_nonrange
2	0	699	1	52	1161
3	2	711	4	21	555
36	6	133	35	27	1760
38	0	29	37	35	239
39	2	110	40	207	1264

Figure 9 displays the results for multiple ecoregions, along with their corresponding confidence intervals, where the variance estimates have been obtained through the Jackknife method.

Figure 9: Rangeland Ecoregion Level Estimates and CI

5 Results for Pastureland Estimation

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the Random Forest, LGBM, SVM, and Lasso models specifically for pastureland data, utilizing the dataset from Arkansas. The Arkansas dataset is selected due to the availability of an adequate number of sample points. We explore the effect of varying square tile sizes on prediction accuracy and conclude that a 7×7 pixel grid offers the most reliable outcomes. Subsequently, we provide a detailed comparison of the prediction accuracy across the LASSO, LGBM, SVM, and Random Forest models, utilizing the datasets from 48 U.S. states and 85 Ecoregion level 3 areas to evaluate their respective effectiveness in estimating pastureland. The dataset selection is based on the widespread presence of pastureland and the prevalence of grazing activities across these regions. The analysis is confined to the 48 contiguous states due to the absence of available or sufficient data from Alaska and Hawaii.

Our results demonstrate that integrating the Random Forest model with the 7×7 square tile size yields the highest accuracy for pastureland estimates, consistent with the findings for rangeland. Moreover, the Jackknife method proves to be equally effective for variance estimation of pastureland at the Ecoregion Level 3.

5.1 Comparison of Various Models and Datasets Across Multiple Square Tile Sizes

We performed a comparative analysis using the pastureland dataset from Arkansas, examining the impact of square tile sizes of 1×1 , 3×3 , 5×5 , and 7×7 on model performance. A 10-fold cross-validation approach was employed to assess and compare the predictive accuracy of four models: a logistic regression model with LASSO regularization, LightGBM, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Random Forest.

Table 8 summarizes the mean AUC values across 16 distinct scenarios, providing a comparison of model performance based on varying square tile sizes and methodologies. The results reveal a consistent pattern: larger square tiles tend to result in higher AUC values, indicating their ability to capture more pertinent information for improving prediction accuracy. This pattern aligns with the findings from the rangeland dataset. Consequently, for the imputation estimation of pastureland acreage, we have chosen to use data obtained from the largest square tiles.

The Random Forest model demonstrated exceptional performance among the evaluated models, consistently achieving AUC values exceeding 0.94, reflecting its high classification accuracy. This notable result confirms Random Forest as the most suitable choice for our analysis.

Table 8: Mean AUCs of Arkansas

Size	LightGBM	SVM	Random Forest	LASSO min
1×1	0.9049	0.8725	0.9070	0.9050
3×3	0.9355	0.9115	0.9388	0.9348
5×5	0.9377	0.9114	0.9392	0.9342
7×7	0.9388	0.9160	0.9410	0.9331

5.2 County-level estimates

Utilizing the plug-in imputation estimator and aggregating CDL data with 7×7 grid sections, we calculated county-level estimates for all counties within Arkansas. The county-level estimates for pastureland, presented in Figure 10, differ from those of rangeland due to the lower percentage of NRI sample points identified as pastureland. As a result, the figure does not exhibit the same high degree of alignment between the model-based and design-based estimates as observed with the rangeland data. However, there is still a reasonable level of consistency between the two estimation approaches. Notably, the LGBM model demonstrates an overestimation of pastureland acreage, similar to its performance in the rangeland estimates. Despite these differences, the overall consistency of the model-based approach remains evident.

Figure 10: Estimates of the pastureland area in each county in Arkansas.

5.3 State-level estimates

Building upon the county-level analysis, we extended our evaluation to the state level, examining model performance across 48 U.S. states. Table 9 presents the NRI sample sizes, along with a detailed breakdown of pastureland and non-pastureland data points, for each of the 48 states.

Table 9: NRI sample sizes, and the breakdown into pastureland and non-pastureland data points across 48 states

State	Sample	Pasture	NonPasture	State	Sample	Pasture	NonPasture
Alabama	4048	524	3524	Nebraska	5097	321	4776
Arizona	1616	19	1597	Nevada	1638	57	1581
Arkansas	3625	497	3128	New Hampshire	1444	25	1419
California	5971	222	5749	New Jersey	1582	60	1522
Colorado	4826	251	4575	New Mexico	3434	156	3278
Connecticut	1275	47	1228	New York	4701	440	4261
Delaware	839	29	810	North Carolina	4432	307	4125
Florida	5532	580	4952	North Dakota	5898	399	5499
Georgia	4592	345	4247	Ohio	4673	414	4259
Idaho	4500	457	4043	Oklahoma	4447	1061	3386
Illinois	6413	472	5941	Oregon	3709	366	3343
Indiana	4365	342	4023	Pennsylvania	5056	454	4602
Iowa	5117	590	4527	Rhode Island	806	21	785
Kansas	5816	565	5251	South Carolina	3473	195	3278
Kentucky	4127	761	3366	South Dakota	5249	254	4995
Louisiana	3917	482	3435	Tennessee	4274	677	3597
Maine	1564	43	1521	Texas	13670	1902	11768
Maryland	2830	205	2625	Utah	1826	216	1610
Massachusetts	1724	45	1679	Vermont	1553	136	1417
Michigan	6051	414	5637	Virginia	4935	484	4451
Minnesota	6831	585	6246	Washington	3789	226	3563
Mississippi	4796	543	4253	West Virginia	2339	254	2085
Missouri	6167	1335	4832	Wisconsin	5340	507	4833
Montana	4314	524	3790	Wyoming	2629	224	2405

Utilizing the pastureland dataset, we assessed the accuracy of each model by calculating the mean AUC values for each state, applying a 10-fold cross-validation approach to ensure reliable evaluation.

Figure 11: Mean AUC of 45 States

Figure 11 displays the box plots of the mean AUC values for four models across 48 U.S. states, offering a comparative analysis of each model's performance. The Random Forest, LightGBM, and Lasso models exhibit relatively consistent performance with higher median AUC values, whereas the SVM model shows greater variability and a lower median AUC. These results suggest that the Random Forest, LightGBM, and Lasso models provide more stable and accurate predictions for pastureland estimation across the 48 states, while SVM demonstrates a wider spread in its performance.

Figure 12: Estimates of the pastureland area in each state

Figure 12 provides a comparison between design-based and model-based estimates of pastureland acreage across 48 U.S. states. The results demonstrate a strong alignment between the Random Forest, Lasso, and SVM models and the design-based estimates, highlighting the accuracy and ef-

fectiveness of these model-based approaches. In contrast, the LGBM model tends to overestimate pastureland acreage. This comparison underscores the reliability of Random Forest, Lasso, and SVM for state-level pastureland estimation.

5.4 Ecoregion Level 3 Model estimates

Shifting from the county and state-level analyses, we now turn our attention to Ecoregion Level 3, which serves as the primary focus of this project. In this analysis, we utilize the pastureland dataset and apply LASSO, Random Forest, SVM, and LGBM models, with CDL data aggregated using 7×7 grid sections. Table 10 presents the NRI sample sizes, along with a breakdown of pastureland and non-pastureland data points, for each of the Ecoregion Level 3 areas.

Table 10 indicates that the Ecoregion Level 3 area 79 has an insufficient number of NRI points classified as pastureland, posing challenges for reliably fitting the model. To address this limitation, we combined Ecoregion Level 3 area 79 with adjacent regions that yield state-level estimators more consistent with the NRI estimators, specifically Ecoregion Level 3 area 81.

Table 11 presents the number of square tiles (each composed of 7×7 pixels) for each of the Ecoregion Level 3 areas.

Figure 13 and figure 14 display comparisons between design-based and model-based estimates of pastureland acreage at both the county and state levels across 48 U.S. states. The model-based estimates are generated using CDL data aggregated into 7×7 grid sections, with the Random Forest model selected due to its superior performance in the previous analysis. For these model-based estimates, an Ecoregion Level 3 modeling approach was employed, where different models were fitted for each ecoregion, allowing for varying coefficients across regions. Consistent with the methodology outlined in Section 4.4, this approach was necessary because design-based estimates are only available at the county and state levels, without Ecoregion Level 3 specificity. The figures also present confidence intervals for the design-based estimates, with variance calculated via the Jackknife method.

It is important to note that the consistency between model-based and design-based estimates is not as strong as observed for rangeland, primarily due to the significantly smaller number of NRI sample points identified as pastureland. Nonetheless, there remains a reasonable level of consistency, and we believe that our model provides a viable alternative for pastureland estimation.

Table 10: NRI sample sizes, and the breakdown into pastureland and non-pastureland data points across Ecoregion Level 3 areas.

Eco	Sample	Pasture	NonPasture	Eco	Sample	Pasture	NonPasture
1	1163	99	1064	44	444	9	435
2	699	105	594	45	5079	531	4548
3	713	105	608	46	5165	426	4739
4	576	6	570	47	9083	852	8231
5	452	4	448	48	1216	81	1135
6	1690	71	1619	49	417	25	392
7	1373	83	1290	50	3844	173	3671
8	121	32	89	51	2995	323	2672
9	683	178	505	52	1832	202	1630
10	2121	75	2046	53	1195	120	1075
11	817	66	751	54	4120	341	3779
12	1935	220	1715	55	2984	216	2768
13	2233	478	1755	56	4946	638	4308
14	701	3	698	57	2947	172	2775
15	934	85	849	58	4274	183	4091
16	279	94	185	59	3533	152	3381
17	1583	191	1392	60	3639	232	3407
18	1463	51	1412	61	636	31	605
19	523	64	459	62	5126	159	4967
20	1296	97	1199	63	2561	252	2309
21	1853	177	1676	64	2961	312	2649
22	1302	64	1238	65	12931	123	11808
23	415	13	402	66	4595	685	3910
24	1294	13	1281	67	4559	685	3910
25	6973	426	6547	68	1100	177	923
26	3085	161	2924	69	2137	180	1957
27	6542	531	6011	70	3023	404	2619
28	568	63	505	71	5117	1119	3998
29	217	53	164	72	5221	513	4708
30	755	35	720	73	4233	174	4059
31	1579	45	1534	74	2266	298	1968
32	1035	38	997	75	5941	547	5394
33	1394	507	887	76	490	15	475
34	311	473	2698	77	156	41	115
35	4234	762	3472	78	692	61	631
36	375	60	315	79	424	2	422
37	570	38	532	80	1719	100	1619
38	152	34	118	81	1115	4	1111
39	2107	664	3553	82	974	38	936
40	4866	1134	3552	83	1787	196	1591
41	51	4	47	84	1172	34	1138
42	4114	255	3859	85	478	9	469
43	4912	411	4501				

Table 11: Number of square tiles across Ecoregion Level 3 areas

Eco	Square Tiles	Eco	Square Tiles	Eco	Square Tiles
1	1270359	30	1713367	58	2843024
2	449082	31	1219697	59	988850
3	341545	32	993148	60	1065256
4	1345120	33	1280842	61	709245
5	1215110	34	1879245	62	612325
6	1777921	35	3493447	63	2269126
7	1062630	36	615057	64	721949
8	360417	37	652048	65	7569342
9	1212874	38	324921	66	1076450
10	1900385	39	2435539	67	2682992
11	1619428	40	2616384	68	874355
12	1228089	41	432231	69	1430040
13	7029641	42	3989711	70	1872667
14	2904401	43	8161186	71	2847682
15	1873036	44	1347759	72	2768844
16	1377020	45	3824804	73	2809222
17	3757724	46	3077340	74	1188275
18	3018318	47	5221077	75	3364064
19	1047273	48	1029832	76	532743
20	3113135	49	520489	77	693948
21	3324792	50	4387756	78	1104436
22	3267640	51	903028	79	903028
23	2517179	52	1084425	80	3191556
24	3739650	53	746392	81	2695456
25	6566058	54	1752118	82	1047224
26	4533796	55	2035859	83	929365
27	6286607	56	1215091	84	368084
28	638526	57	741576	85	480857
29	2019895				

Figure 13: Pastureland County Level Estimates

Figure 14: Pastureland State Level Estimates

The imputed map in Figure 15 outlines Ecoregion Level 3 boundaries and depicts the predicted probability of pastureland across the 48 states examined in this study. This map serves as a valuable tool by offering a probabilistic overview of pastureland distribution, enabling the identification and extraction of specific regions of interest from which pastureland acreage can be accurately calculated. Additionally, the map allows us to verify that the area identified as pastureland is significantly smaller than that of rangeland, reinforcing the challenges associated with fitting models and estimating pastureland acreage.

Figure 15: Ecoregion boundaries and the predicted probability of rangeland

5.5 Ecoregion Level 3 estimates with Confidence Interval

In the study by Jang et al. (2024), the variance of (9) was calculated using a parametric bootstrap approach, which depends on the assumption of balanced classification within the dataset. However, this assumption is not met at the Ecoregion Level 3 for pastureland estimation, where the dataset is highly imbalanced due to the majority of data points being classified as non-pastureland. This imbalance in the dataset complicates variance estimation, particularly when the number of data points classified as pastureland is significantly limited. As a result, in this study, we apply the Jackknife method to estimate the variance of (9).

The Jackknife approach and specific details used to calculate the variance follow the methodology outlined in Section 4.6. Figure 16 presents the results for several ecoregions, along with their corresponding confidence intervals, where the variance estimation is derived using the Jackknife method.

Figure 16: Pastureland Ecoregion Level Estimates and CI

6 Discussion

In this study, we developed robust model-based estimators by integrating NRI survey data with CDL auxiliary data to accurately estimate the total area of rangeland and pastureland at the Ecoregion Level 3. Unlike traditional methods that rely on sampling weights and predefined sampling units, our approach employs a fine grid of square tiles to aggregate CDL data, enabling flexible application to arbitrary target regions. This method offers a substantial advantage by eliminating the dependency on specific NRI sampling units, thus providing a more adaptable framework for estimating land area across diverse geographic regions.

By employing LASSO, Random Forest, LGBM, and SVM models, our empirical analysis revealed that the Random Forest model consistently delivered superior prediction accuracy. This was validated through the use of the AUC metric, which demonstrated the model's effectiveness in classifying rangeland and pastureland areas with high precision. Additionally, the Random Forest model exhibited relatively small biases compared to the other approaches, further reinforcing its reliability for accurate acreage estimation. These findings suggest that the Random Forest model offers a robust and dependable solution for land area estimation in varying ecoregions.

Moreover, the flexibility of our approach allows it to be applied beyond traditional state or Ecoregion Level 3 boundaries, making it suitable for a wide range of geographic areas. By leveraging the grid-based CDL data aggregation, this method can be easily adapted to estimate land areas for any arbitrary region, regardless of predefined administrative or ecological boundaries. Further research could explore additional applications in ecological assessments and build upon the methodological framework presented here, potentially expanding its utility for various environmental and resource management scenarios.

A Appendix A: Adjustment Method for Aligning Estimates with NRI Data

This section addresses the scenario where there is a need for the state-level rangeland estimates generated in this study to match those released by the National Resources Inventory (NRI). Given the use of different datasets and methodologies in our study, it is reasonable for the estimates to differ from those provided by the NRI. However, in cases where alignment with the NRI estimates

is required, this section introduces a method for adjusting our estimates to achieve consistency with the NRI's published data. It is also important to note that the adjustment method introduced in this section is specifically designed for application within the Lasso model and may not be directly applicable to other modeling approaches.

Building on the preceding information, the plug-in imputation estimator of T , denoted as $\hat{T}_m(\hat{\beta})$, is calculated as follows:

$$\hat{T}_m(\hat{\beta}) = \sum_{i=1}^N mW_i(1 - \eta_i) \left\{ \delta_i Y_i + (1 - \delta_i) \hat{P}(Y_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_i; \hat{\beta}) \right\}. \quad (14)$$

To achieve the objective of this section, we solve the function (15) for γ_j corresponding to state j as follows:

$$\hat{T}_{\text{NRI},j} = \sum_{i(j)=1}^{n_j} mW_{i(j)}(1 - \eta_{i(j)}) \left\{ \delta_{i(j)} Y_{i(j)} + (1 - \delta_{i(j)}) \tilde{P}(Y_{i(j)} = 1 | \mathbf{X}_{i(j)}; \gamma_j; \hat{\beta}_j) \right\}, \quad (15)$$

where $i(j) = 1, \dots, n_j$ represents the total number of grid cells that intersect with state j , $\hat{T}_{\text{NRI},j}$ denotes the state-level rangeland estimates released by the NRI, and

$$\tilde{P}(Y_{i(j)} = 1 | \mathbf{X}_{i(j)}; \gamma_j; \hat{\beta}_j) = \frac{\exp(\gamma_j + X_{i(j)} \hat{\beta}_j)}{1 + \exp(\gamma_j + X_{i(j)} \hat{\beta}_j)}. \quad (16)$$

After obtaining $\hat{\gamma}_j$, we can compute $\hat{P}(Y_{i(j)} = 1 | \mathbf{X}_{i(j)}, \hat{\gamma}_j, \hat{\beta}_j)$ for each grid cell. This allows us to derive the adjusted model-based estimates not only for state-level rangeland but also for any specific region of interest. By applying these adjustments, we ensure that the estimates align more closely with the NRI's state-level data while maintaining flexibility for application. This method enhances the reliability and consistency of our model-based estimates, making them more comparable to the established benchmarks provided by the NRI.

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